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THE PROBLEM OF SOIL POLLUTION AND DEGRADATION ON THE TERRITORY OF BELARUS FOR THE PERIOD 2015-2016

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Annotation: The problem of land degradation due to various anthropogenic factors was studied, as a result of the study, the causes of land degradation in Belarus were identified and their impact on human health was studied. The soils of the surveyed settlements are characterized by exceeding the values of background concentrations for all identified ingredients, which confirms the accumulation of man-made pollutants in the upper layer of urban soils, and there has also been a deterioration in the agrophysical state of soils due to erosion and reclamation.

Keywords: soil, land degradation, anthropogenic factors

ПРОБЛЕМА ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЯ И ДЕГРАДАЦИИ ПОЧВ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ БЕЛАРУСИ ЗА ПЕРИОД 2015-2016 ГГ.

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Аннотация: Изучена проблема деградации земель вследствие различных антропогенных факторов, в результате проведенного исследования были установлены причины деградации земель в Беларуси и изучено их влияние на здоровье человека. Для почв обследованных населенных пунктов характерно превышение значений фоновых концентраций по всем определяемым ингредиентам, что подтверждает факт накопления техногенных загрязняющих веществ в верхнем слое городских почв, также произошло ухудшение агрофизического состояния почв, вследствие эрозии и мелиорации.

Ключевые слова: почва, деградация земель, антропогенные факторы

Relevance. One of the foundations of sustainable development of any country is the organization of rational use and protection of natural resources, of which the soil is an integral part.

In ecological terms, soil is the most important ecological link that, through climate, food, air and water, ensures human survival in a given area, forms his health, morbid status and life span [1-3].

Soil is not a renewable resource, i.e. in case of loss or degradation, it cannot be restored in a time comparable to the duration of human life. It is necessary to recognize the value of soils, their productive potential and contribution to food security and the maintenance of key ecosystem services [3-5]. Here are just a few reasons why the problem of soil pollution should not be underestimated.

Soil pollution affects everything around. The food we eat, the water we drink, the air we breathe – our health and the health of all life on the planet depends on the health of the soils.

Soil contamination may be the result of improper farming practices. Irrational farming methods reduce the reserves of soil organic matter, undermining their ability to decompose organic pollutants. This increases the risk of pollutants entering the environment.

The purpose of the study. To study the problem of land degradation due to various anthropogenic factors.

Materials and methods of research. Analytical and comparative-evaluative research methods were used in the work.

These lands require constant monitoring and monitoring of their condition. Such observations are systematically carried out within the framework of the National Environmental Monitoring System in accordance with the CCP in force since 2008 17.13–02–2008 "Environmental protection and nature management. Environmental monitoring. The procedure for conducting observations of chemical pollution of lands", which regulates the procedure for conducting observations on background territories, lands of settlements, agricultural lands and lands of roadside lanes.

Results and their discussion. On the territory of Belarus, land degradation occurs as a result of many factors. In particular, due to water and wind erosion, chemical pollution of land in settlements, along roads, in areas affected by industrial and municipal waste landfills, radiation pollution in the exclusion zone as a result of the Chernobyl accident. To this should be added the transformation of sod-podzolic soils during their long-term agricultural use, as well as as a result of mining, cultural works, road, urban and other types of construction, irrational use of forest lands.

The area of eroded lands on the territory of Belarus is more than 550 thousand hectares or 2.7 % of the country's area, land with potentially possible soil washout is more than 1400 thousand hectares or 7.0 %.

The large-scale drainage reclamation carried out in 1960-1980 on the territory of Belarus led to a change in the natural processes of the formation of swamps and wetlands and caused a number of environmental problems. In recent years, reclamation development of new lands is practically not conducted. The Brest region is characterized by the largest areas of reclaimed territories – more than 1/5 of the total area of the region, the smallest – Mogilev, where the share of reclaimed land accounts for 12.0 %.

A big role in soil degradation is its pollution as a result of man-made processes: the increase in the volume of mining, the development of energy, the chemicalization of agriculture. Pollutants enter the soil with precipitation, dust, gases, sewage. The main pollutants are organic and mineral acids (sulfuric, hydrochloric, nitric), heavy metals, petroleum products.

The data of observations of the soils of settlements indicate that the soils of a number of surveyed cities are characterized by exceeding the values of MPC or APC for heavy metals: lead (with a maximum of 3.5 MPC and 2.5 MPC in the cities of Mogilev and Vitebsk, respectively), zinc (with a maximum of 3.9 MPC and 2.2 MPC in the cities of Mogilev and Vitebsk, respectively), zinc (with a maximum of 3.9 MPC and 2.2 MPC in the cities

of Mogilev and Vitebsk, respectively), cadmium (with a maximum in Molodechno), copper (with a maximum of 2.5 MPC and 2.5 MPC in Vitebsk).

The soils of the surveyed cities are characterized by exceeding the values of background concentrations of lead, zinc, copper, nickel, cadmium, chromium, sulfates and nitrates, which confirms the accumulation of man-made pollutants in the upper layer of urban soils.

Values exceeding the MPC for petroleum products in soils were noted for all surveyed cities. The largest areas of pollution are typical for Vitebsk, Molodechno and Gomel (76.0 %, 66.7 % and 35.0 % of samples analyzed in the city, respectively). The average values are at the level of 0.7-1.8 MPC. The maximum values were registered in Vitebsk, Molodechno and Novopolotsk at a level above 6.6 MPC, and 3.9 MPC and 3.7 MPC, respectively.

Observations of the soils of roadside lanes of highways revealed the dependence of the degree of soil pollution on the intensity of traffic for lead, its content in the soil increases by an average of 6-40 % with an increase in the intensity of traffic from 1 to 16 thousand cars per day. A similar dependence can also be traced for cadmium, copper. The MPC of the content of technogenic toxicants in roadside soils with distance from the roadbed is traced.

The main pollutants of roadside soils are petroleum products and benzo(a)pyrene. Thus, the maximum content of petroleum products was detected at the 10th removal of profile No. 5 (P-11 Porechany – Novogrudok – Nesvizh) at 366 level 7.2 APC. Significant APC exceedances were also determined at 10 m distances of profile No. 3 (M-8/E-95 border of the Russian Federation – Vitebsk – Gomel – border of Ukraine) at the level of 6.6 APC, profile No. 19 (P-21 Vitebsk – border of the Russian Federation) at the level of 3.6 APC, profile No. 6 (P46 Lepel – Polotsk – border of the Russian Federation) at the level of 3.6 APC. The maximum value of benzo(a)pyrene corresponds to 2.1 MPC (at a distance of 25 m of profile No. 8 – M-8/ E-95 border of the Russian Federation – Vitebsk – Gomel – border of Ukraine, a highway with a traffic intensity of 1888 auth/day).

There were no APC exceedances for heavy metals, as well as nitrates and sulfates in soil samples of roadside lanes of highways.

The average values of nitrates are at the level of 0.01-0.12 MPC. The maximum value is observed in Pinsk and corresponds to 0.8 MPC.

The excess of the quality standard for sulfates at the level of 1.02 to 1.8 MPC was noted in Brest, Pinsk, Lida, Kostyukovichi. The average values of the sulfate content in the soil of cities correspond to 0.4-0.7 MPC. The percentage of analyzed soil samples with the content of detectable pollutants exceeding the MPC (APC) ranged from 2 and 2.9 in Brest and Pinsk to 11.4 and 28.0 in Lida and Kostyukovichi. The largest areas of pollution are characteristic of Lida and Kostyukovichi (11.4 % and 28.0 % of samples analyzed in the city, respectively).

Conclusions. Thus, as a result of the conducted research, the causes of land degradation in Belarus were identified and their impact on human health was studied. The soils of the surveyed settlements are characterized by exceeding the values of background concentrations for all identified ingredients, which confirms the accumulation of man-made pollutants in the upper layer of urban soils, and there has also been a deterioration in the agrophysical state of soils due to erosion and reclamation.

Bibliography

[1] Regulations on the procedure for conducting land monitoring and the use of its data as part of the NSEM in the Republic of Belarus // Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus dated March 28, 2007 No. 386.

[2] Instructions on the organization of work on land monitoring // Resolution of the State Committee on Property of the Republic of Belarus dated December 22, 2009 No. 68.

[3] Maximum permissible concentrations of petroleum products in lands (including soils) for various categories of lands // Decree of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus dated March 12, 2012 No. 17/1.

[4] Hygienic standards 2.1.5.10-21-2003 "Maximum Permissible Concentrations (MPC) of chemicals in the water of water bodies for drinking and domestic water use".

[5] Zimatkina T.I. Environmental medicine: a workshop for students studying in the specialties 1-79 01 01 "General Medicine", 1-79 01 02 "Pediatrics" / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich, G.D. Smirnova. – Grodno: GrGMU, 2020. 32 p.

Список литературы

[1] Положение о порядке проведения в составе НСМОС в Республике Беларусь мониторинга земель и использования его данных // постановление Совета Министров Республики Беларусь от 28 марта 2007 г. №386.

[2] Инструкция об организации работ по проведению мониторинга земель // постановление Государственного комитета по имуществу Республики Беларусь от 22 декабря 2009 г. № 68.

[3] Предельно допустимые концентрации нефтепродуктов в землях (включая почвы) для различных категорий земель // постановление Министерства здравоохранения Республики Беларусь от 12 марта 2012 г. № 17/1.

[4] Гигиенические нормативы 2.1.5.10-21-2003 «Предельно допустимые концентрации (ПДК) химических веществ в воде водных объектов хозяйственно-питьевого и культурно-бытового водопользования».

[5] Зиматкина Т.И. Экологическая медицина: практикум для студентов, обучающихся по специальностям 1-79 01 01 «Лечебное дело», 1-79 01 02 «Педиатрия» / Т.И. Зиматкина, А.С. Александрович, Г.Д. Смирнова. – Гродно: ГрГМУ, 2020. 32 с.

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